

FABRICATION AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF COMPO-CASTING $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ /MAGNESIUM ALLOY

Gen Sasaki ¹, Makoto Yoshida ¹, Jin Pan ¹, Hideharu Fukunaga ¹
Nobuyuki Fuyama ² and Toshio Fujii ²

¹ Dept. of Mech. Eng., Hiroshima University, Higashi-Hiroshima 739-8527, Japan

² Western Hiroshima Pref. Industrial Res. Inst., Kure 737-0004, Japan

SUMMARY: $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particle and whisker reinforced magnesium alloy (AZ91D and ZK60) composites were fabricated by the compocasting. Some composites were extruded at 400, or injection- molded after casting. As-cast composites have low strength because of high porosity and large α phase grain. But the reinforcement distributed in the post-liquid phase in the matrix uniformly. By hot extrusion or semi-solid injection molding, the strength of the composites increased dramatically. On the other hand, AZ91D matrix composites exhibit good age hardening ability because of good heat-stability of interface structure between reinforcement and matrix.

KEYWORDS: Magnesium, Aluminum borate, Particle, Whisker, Compocasting

INTRODUCTION

In the transport industry such as the automobile, train and airplane, the lightening of the machine parts has been developed. Therefore, magnesium alloys are watched as the suitable alternate for iron, steel and aluminum alloy. But magnesium alloys are inferior to aluminum and titanium alloys in rigidity and wear resistance. In order to improve these mechanical properties, the combination to ceramics is needed. Actually, particle, whisker and fiber of SiC Al_2O_3 and carbon have been examined for reinforcements of the magnesium matrix composites. Especially, SiC particle and whisker are suitable for the reinforcement of practical magnesium alloy [1,2]. On the other hand, $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ ceramics has been envisaged as reinforcement of aluminum alloy [3]. $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ ceramics has good mechanical properties and high cost performance. Actually, some composites are used in automobile engine piston. Recently, it was found that this reinforcement is good for magnesium alloys [4]. But the treatments of the molten magnesium alloys are difficult because of the heavy oxidation and self-combustibility. Recently, the semi-solid casting for magnesium alloys has been developed.

In this study, in order to obtain high performance magnesium alloy matrix composites, $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ /magnesium alloy composites were fabricated by compocasting and the relationship between process condition and microstructure was investigated.

COMPOSITE FABRICATION

$\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particles (PC-8, Shikoku chemicals Co., Average particle size: 8 μm) and whiskers (M-20, Shikoku chemicals Co., Diameter: 0.5-1.0 μm , Length: 10-30 μm) were used

for the reinforcement of the composite. The matrices were AZ91D and ZK60 alloys, which compositions are Mg-9.0%Al-0.68%Zn and Mg-5.5%Zn-0.4%Zr, respectively. The volume fraction of the reinforcement in the composites was 5-15 %. The solid fraction of the matrix in the compo-casting process was 30-33%. Some composites were hot-worked in order improve the porosity, that is, extrusion at 400, or semi-solid injection molding after casting.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND MICROSTRUCTURE

Table 1 shows the tensile strength and the porosity of the composites. The tensile strength of the as-cast $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ particle /AZ91D composite is very low and almost equal to that of the monolithic alloy. It is caused by the high porosity (about 5%). In order to improve the strength of the composites, extrusion and semi-solid injection molding were carried out. By semi-solid injection molding after casting, the strength of $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ particle /AZ91D composite improved dramatically to 277 MPa and the porosity decrease to almost 0%. $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ whisker /AZ91D composite after injection molding and $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composite after extrusion are very high strength because of 0% porosity.

Fig. 1 shows the microstructure of as-cast $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ whisker and particle /AZ91D composites, respectively. The bright circular region and bright/dark region in figure are α magnesium solid phase and post liquid phase, respectively. The dark parts in bright/dark region are the reinforcements and it distribute uniformly in post-liquid phase without coalescence. α magnesium solid phase is about 100 μ m in diameter, which is very large compared with that of monolithic alloy fabricated by melt casting. The circular black regions

Table 1 Tensile strength and porosity of $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ /magnesium alloy composites prepared by compocasting.

Processing		Matrix	Reinforcement Vf (%)	Solid fraction Fs (%)	Porosity (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Compo-casting (Melt stirring and ingot casting)	As-cast	AZ91D	Particle (5)	33	3.9	160
	Semi-solid forming		Particle (5)	33	0	277
			Whisker (5)	33	0	292
	Extruded	ZK60	Whisker (5)	0	4.7	---
				30	5.2	---
			Whisker (5)	0	0	322
			30	0	302	

Fig. 1 Microstructure of as-cast $Al_{18}B_4O_{33}$ (a) whisker and (b) particle /AZ91D composites.

are pores, which size is 50-200 μm in diameter. The composites have inhomogeneous microstructure and many defects. The large sized α magnesium solid phase and many pores seem to lead to the degradation of the composite strength.

On the other hand, there is the possibility of the damage of the whisker because of the interfacial reaction during the fabrication, if the matrix contains Mg and Al elements [3]. Fig. 2 shows the microstructure around the interface between whisker and matrix in as-cast $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /AZ91D composite. There is the uniform interfacial reaction layer with 10-20nm in thickness. This layer grew on the whisker epitaxially and covered with the whisker completely. As this uniform reaction layer prevents the direct reaction between the whisker and matrix at high temperature, the degradation of the mechanical properties by heat treatment is not observed.

Fig. 2 Microstructure around the interface between the whisker and matrix alloy in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /AZ91D composite.

Fig. 3 shows the microstructure of as-cast $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composite. The whisker distributed uniformly without coalescence, but there are many pores 10-100 μm in diameter.

Fig. 3. Microstructure of as-cast $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composite.

Anal ysis point	Element (at.%)				
	Al	Mg	O	Zr	Zn
1	45.54	5.46	49.00	0.00	0.00
2	46.71	5.45	47.85	0.00	0.00
3	19.10	38.06	22.18	5.44	15.22
4	13.93	41.80	15.99	7.05	21.24
5	0.55	90.11	7.20	0.01	2.12
6	0.56	96.60	0.81	0.06	1.97

Fig. 4 Microstructure and EDS analysis around the interface between the whisker and matrix in $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ /ZK60 composite.

Actually, the porosity of this composite is 5.2% and it seems that this composite has low strength.

Fig. 4 shows the microstructure and EDS analysis of as-cast $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composite. There is uniform reaction layer with 10-20nm in thickness between whisker and matrix. This reaction layer contains Al, Mg, O, Zr, and Zn elements. The concentration of Zr and Zn elements are 5-7at% and 15-21at%, respectively. This layer seems complex oxide of Al, Mg, Zr and Zn with polycrystalline, but the reaction layer could not be identified. This layer prevents the direct reaction between the whisker and the matrix, but reactive compared with MgAl_2O_4 layer in AZ91D matrix composite. Many Zr and Zn elements in the matrix were consumed in the interfacial reaction during the compocasting and heat-treatment after casting.

Fig.5 shows the age hardening curves of the monolithic AZ91D, ZK60 and $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /AZ91D, $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composites. $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /AZ91D composite exhibit good age hardening ability. Times to reach the peak hardness of the monolithic alloy and the composite were 1×10^5 s and 1×10^4 s, respectively. It is caused by interfacial stress resulting from the difference in the thermal expansion coefficients between the whisker and the matrix. In $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ and AZ91D system, $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ react with magnesium to form MgAl_2O_4 . But there was a uniform and very thin reaction layer after casting. As the reactivity between whisker and matrix is low, the composition of the matrix remains almost unchanged by the composite fabrication and heat-treatment after casting. On the other hand, the age hardening ability of

Fig 5. Age hardening curves of the monolithic alloy and composites. The $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /AZ91D composite in this figure was fabricated by semi-solid squeeze casting and the volume fraction of the reinforcement in the composite is 25%.

Fig. 6. Microstructure of hot-worked composites after casting. (a) injected $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particle /AZ91D and (b) extruded $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composites.

$\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composite is low compared with the monolithic ZK60 alloy. The shortening of peak time are not occurred. In this composite, it seems that many Zr and Zn element, which need for age hardening, are consumed in the interfacial reaction during casting and heat-treatment after casting.

In usual, the compocasting composites hot work in order to improve the mechanical properties. Fig. 6 shows the microstructure of the hot-worked composites after casting. $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /AZ91D composite was injection-molded at semi-solid condition after casting. Fig. 6 (a) shows the microstructure of the injection-molded composites. The pores disappeared and the size of the bright circular and bright/dark regions became to be fine. It leads to improve the tensile strength. On the other hand, $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composite was extruded at 400°C. Fig.6 (b) shows the microstructure of the extruded composite. The matrix grains in the composite elongated along the extrusion direction and became to be fine in the cross section of the extrusion direction. The porosity decreased to 0%. The whisker aligned along extrusion direction without coalescence. It seems that the strength of the composite improve because of the decrease of the porosity, the grain refinement and the work hardening.

CONCLUSIONS

$\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ particles and whiskers reinforced AZ91D and ZK60 alloy composites were fabricated by the compocasting. The microstructure and the mechanical properties of the composites were investigated.

- 1) The reinforcements in both composites distribute uniformly in the post liquid phase but there are many pores 50-200 μm in diameter. Extrusion and semi-solid injection molding after casting were improve the strength of the composite because of the work hardening and the decrease of the pores and the grain refinement.
- 2) $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /AZ91D composites exhibit good age hardening ability because of the low reactivity between whisker and matrix. $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ react with magnesium to form a uniform reaction layer (MgAl_2O_4) 20-30 nm in thickness after casting. This reaction layer prevents a further interfacial reaction. On the other hand, the age hardening ability of $\text{Al}_{18}\text{B}_4\text{O}_{33}$ whisker /ZK60 composite is low because of the reactive interfacial reaction compared with AZ91D matrix composite.

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